

MultiXscale

Report on the current scalability of ESPResSo and the planned work to extend it

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes the results from High Performance Computing (HPC) benchmarks for the molecular dynamics and fluid dynamics software ESPResSo and outlines the planned work to reach pre-exascale readiness:

- *Scalability study* (Section 2) measures the performance characteristics of ESPResSo on the petascale HPC facility “Vega” for a variety of simulation setups that are relevant to ionic liquid-based battery design, charged soft matter research, and liquid systems research. In particular, these are:
 1. molecular dynamics of particles interacting via the Lennard-Jones potential,
 2. molecular dynamics of particles that additionally carry a charge, with P³M as the electrostatics solver,
 3. lattice-Boltzmann hydrodynamics.

Performance bottlenecks are identified and their root cause explained. Most notably these are:

1. avoidable synchronization barriers in the short-range force calculation,
 2. limited scalability of the MPI-based three-dimensional FFT used in the P³M algorithm,
 3. lack of multi-GPU support in ESPResSo.
- *Pathway to exascale* (Section 3) outlines major structural changes that are necessary for ESPResSo to become competitive on pre-exascale systems. The impact of proposed changes are discussed in the light of benchmark studies of code libraries used by ESPResSo and molecular dynamics software that are similar to ESPResSo in their design. Resource usage on pre-exascale systems for multiscale simulations are estimated for a concrete usage scenario in energy materials research.

The specific short to medium-term development goals for ESPResSo from this discussion can be summarised as:

- improving the weak scaling characteristics by removing synchronization barriers in the communication,
- optimizing the Verlet list management to avoid superfluous cache invalidation, partitioning the Verlet lists such that they get updated on a per-particle basis, and only when necessary,
- optimize the memory layout of the particles to improve node-level performance,
- eliminate reduction operations for forces and torques by treating local particles and ghost particles differently,
- adapt the short-range force kernels to use SoA data layouts,
- implement a new GPU implementation in ESPResSo that scales well with the number of available GPU devices,
- implement a parallel input/output feature will be written to read and write simulation trajectories in a standardized and portable format, with the goal of improving interoperability between ESPResSo and the other simulation codes involved in MultiXscale.

We conclude by outlining a simulation campaign as it is envisioned for the demonstrator of ESPResSo, which would consist of parameter sweeps over properties such as ion concentration and electrode properties, resulting in approximately 100 parameter sets. For each of these parameter sets, an average over 5 to 10 simulations is taken, to account for the stochastic nature of the simulations resulting from Brownian motion. Hence 500 to 1000 simulations would be run.

For ESPResSo 4.2.1, a simulation with one million charged particles on 1024 cores will currently takes 20 ms per time step, which amounts to 55 hours for a typical simulation length of ten million time steps. In total the simulation campaign described above would therefore consume 30 to 60 million core hours.

Given the current performance of ESPResSo 4.2.1, such campaigns are rarely run. The development work we envision will make such campaigns more feasible:

- Once ESPResSo is capable of making use of the multi-GPU support for the lattice-Boltzmann (LB) method, hydrodynamics can be added to a simulation as described above without increasing the time-to-solution. This would be achieved by off-loading LB to the GPU, for which it is very well suited.
- Reduce the overall time-to-solution with the improvements planned for short-range calculation. If, for example, the efficiency of the electrostatics solver could be improved from 20% to 40% at 1024 cores, the time-to-solution would be halved to approximately one day.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable contains all the elements relevant to Task 2.2, led by the University of Stuttgart. It can be divided into two main parts:

- Task 2.2.1 – measuring the performance characteristics of the most recent release of ESPResSo on a petascale system up to 1000 CPU cores
- Task 2.2.2 – identifying concrete technical solutions to make ESPResSo perform well on pre-exascale systems, in collaboration with our MultiXscale partners

ESPResSo is an open-source particle-based simulation package for molecular dynamics, fluid dynamics and Monte Carlo schemes[1, 2]. It features a wide range of methods for solving electrostatics, magnetostatics, hydrodynamics, electrokinetics and diffusion-advection-reaction equations. It is designed as an MPI-parallel and GPU-accelerated simulation core written in C++ and CUDA, with a scripting interface in Python which integrates well with science and visualization packages in the Python ecosystem, such as numpy and PyOpenGL. Its modularity and extensibility made it a popular tool in soft matter physics, where it has been used to simulate ionic liquids, polyelectrolytes, liquid crystals, colloids, ferrofluids and biological systems such as DNA and lipid membranes.

Many soft matter systems are characterized by physical properties that resolve different time- or length-scales. In order to fully capture these effects in a simulation, a multiscale approach is needed. Often, long-range interactions can be resolved very efficiently with minimal loss of accuracy using grid-based solvers, such as the particle–particle–particle mesh (P^3M) algorithm[3, 4] for electrostatics and magnetostatics. Similarly, solute–solvent interactions can be approximated using the LB method for hydrodynamics, where the dense solvent is discretized on a grid and exchanges momentum with solid particles that represent the solute. These techniques not only bring the computational costs down, they also consume several orders of magnitude less computer memory compared to an atomistically-resolved system, and require less bandwidth during communication between CPU cores.

ESPResSo is equipped with algorithms relevant to multiscale simulations. Resolving large length-scales is achieved by allocating more CPU cores to the problem, with each CPU core being responsible for a small spatial subset of the complete system to keep the computer memory requirements per node within its operational capacity. Resolving large time-scales is achieved via GPU accelerators, which are several orders of magnitude faster than a CPU.

What ESPResSo is currently lacking is the capacity to resolve large time-scales and large length-scales simultaneously. For example, GPU algorithms in ESPResSo can only make use of one GPU per simulation, severely limiting the dimensions of the simulated system. In addition, the P^3M algorithm for electrostatics does not scale well, resulting in a lower efficiency of parallel simulations with hundreds of cores.

In this document, we will report benchmarks for ESPResSo 4.2.1 and discuss how the scalability of the software can be improved. We discuss application scenarios for pre-exascale systems in line with the applications envisioned in MultiXscale. One such application is the study of the capacitance and charging dynamics of nanoporous supercapacitors filled with room-temperature ionic liquids. These energy storage devices are characterized by fast discharge rates and extended longevity compared to conventional capacitors and batteries. However, the diffusive processes that take place during charging and discharging depend heavily on the pore geometry. While idealized models (Figure 1) have been successfully simulated with ESPResSo in the past[5], carbide-derived carbon (CDC) nanoporous materials that can be manufactured on an economically-viable scale often feature defects, such as pores of varying width and interconnected pores[6]. To fully and adequately capture the behavior of the ionic liquid in such an environment, a multiscale approach is needed.

1.2 Target audience

The benchmark results and recommendations of this report are intended for readers with technical expertise in HPC and molecular dynamics, such as users and developers of the ESPResSo software. While benchmark studies have been carried out in the past with a modified version of the software tailored for soot aggregation dynamics[7, 8, 9], this is the first time the performance characteristics of several key algorithms in an unmodified release of ESPResSo are reported.

2 Scalability study

2.1 Initial assessment

To assess the exascale-readiness of Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems (ESPresSo), we ran benchmarks on the HPC Vega supercomputer, the petascale facility based in Slovenia. We simulated various systems of interest for up to 1024 CPU cores and used two complementary metrics: weak scaling efficiency and performance.

Weak scaling efficiency, also known as Gustafson's law[10], measures the capacity of a program to run simulations on a larger length-scale by allocating more CPU resources. It is obtained by dividing the runtime of a simulation of size $n \cdot w$ to which n resources (CPU cores or GPU devices) were allocated, by the runtime of a simulation of size w to which 1 resource was allocated. Thus the problem size per resource, in this case w , remains constant. The efficiency is bounded between 100% and 0%. In an ideal program with no serial component, the efficiency would be 100% for any number of resources allocated to the simulation, assuming the system is homogeneous. Any serial component, e.g. communication overhead between resources, will decrease the efficiency.

Performance measures the capacity of a program to solve large problems in acceptable time-to-solution. It can be expressed, for example, as the number of particles which are propagated per second by a molecular dynamics engine, or as the number of fluid cells which are propagated per second by a LB solver. In an ideal program with no serial component, the performance should scale linearly with the number of resources, if the system is homogeneous.

ESPresSo was originally designed for High Throughput Computing (HTC). As such, it is optimized for simulations on desktop workstations, where resources typically consist of a few dozens CPU cores and a single GPU accelerator. This design choice was motivated by the necessity to carry out ensemble runs, i.e. launching a large number of simulations with slightly different initial conditions and compute ensemble averages of the physico-chemical properties of interest, so as to cover a large portion of the system sample space. While the software has been successfully used for large simulations involving 110 million particles[8], it required custom code to improve load balancing. Our goal is for ESPresSo to run efficiently on petascale HPC environments and be ready for exascale computing.

Figure 1: Coarse-grained simulation of a supercapacitor during the charging step. The ionic liquid (spheres) interact with one another through a LJ potential and a Coulomb potential, and with the CDC material (grey surface) through a LJ potential. The porous material features a reservoir (left) that communicates with a thin slit nanopore (right), whose thickness is slightly larger than the ion diameter. The system extends indefinitely in the x- and y-direction via periodic boundary conditions. An external electric field is applied along the z-direction to force cations (red spheres) to accumulate in the nanopore and anions (blue spheres) to move to the bulk solution. A concentration gradient slowly forms along the z-direction, until the nanopore is completely filled with cations. While such an idealized system can easily be simulated on modern desktop workstations with reasonable time-to-solution, for industrial applications a more realistic description of the nanopore geometry is desirable. High-resolution nanopore topologies based on experimental data require larger system sizes, and give rise to diffusion dynamics with multiple relaxation time scales. Under these conditions, resources from HPC facilities become essential to achieve an acceptable time-to-solution.

2.1.1 Choice of simulation scenarios

We opted for three main simulation scenarios. The Lennard-Jones (LJ) scenario consists of soft spheres interacting with a short-range 12-6 potential. This simple setup underpins most particle-based simulations, where a weakly attractive, strongly repulsive pairwise potential is required to prevent particles from overlapping with one another. In addition, solvated systems with atomistic resolution typically have a large excess of solvent atoms compared to solute atoms, thus LJ interactions tend to account for a large portion of the simulation time.

The ionic liquid scenario is another type of particle-based simulation. It builds upon the LJ scenario and adds an electrical charge to the particles. Since the Coulomb interaction decays with the inverse of the distance, it is necessary to include periodic image contributions to the particle forces. This is achieved using long-range numerical solvers, which leverage the fast Fourier transform (FFT) algorithm to calculate forces in an efficient manner, at the cost of a lower accuracy, whose magnitude can be controlled. This type of simulation finds many applications in soft matter research, such as ionic liquid-based batteries, supercapacitors (Figure 1), and polyelectrolytes (gelling agents, charged biomolecules). In addition, numerical solvers for electrostatics can be easily adapted for magnetostatics, which have further applications magnetic soft matter research, such as ferrofluids and magnetic elastomer actuators (soft robotics).

The hydrodynamics scenario is based on the LB method and models a Newtonian fluid such as water. It was chosen due to the importance of hydrodynamic interactions in many physical systems at the mesoscale. While an atomistic description of solvent molecules is justifiable at the nanoscale, at the scale of micrometers a continuum-based description of the solvent is significantly less computationally demanding. It is also much more accurate than implicit solvent models, which do not adequately capture motion correlation in particles that are close to each other. With hydrodynamics and particle coupling, elements of fluid are resolved on a grid, allowing for momentum transfer between particles mediated via the fluid at the speed of sound.

2.1.2 Technical considerations

We ran the benchmarks on HPC Vega, a Tier-0, 10.1 petaFLOPS peak performance supercomputer. It features 960 nodes equipped with two AMD EPYC Rome 7H12 microprocessors (64 cores, 128 threads, 2.60 GHz), 256 GB of RAM and a 100 Gbps interconnect. There are 60 GPU nodes with similar characteristics, but with double the amount of RAM and four NVIDIA Ampere A100 accelerators.

ESPResSo doesn't use hyperthreading, nor shared memory parallelization. It uses the Message Passing Interface (MPI) with a Cartesian topology. CPU cores are attached to the communicator according to a 3D grid that maps to the spatial domain decomposition of the fluid or particles in the system. To each CPU core corresponds a unique "MPI rank", which starts at zero and increases linearly. In ESPResSo, MPI rank 0 is special: it is the only rank that is able to communicate with the GPU accelerator and with the Python interface.

At every time step, MPI ranks must communicate with their immediate neighbors to exchange particle and fluid information. For example, the LB method must exchange fluid momentum with neighboring fluid domains and update a thin "ghost layer" that contains a copy of the fluid information of the neighboring domain. Likewise, the molecular dynamics engine needs to transfer particles that cross local box boundaries, and update the positions of the "ghost particles", i.e. particles located outside the local box that are necessary to compute pairwise interactions with particles in the local box.

To simulate charged soft matter, an electrostatics solver is needed. The method of choice is the P³M algorithm, which splits the calculation into a real-space contribution (pairwise Coulomb potential) and a Fourier-space contribution (charges interpolated on a grid). The latter can be efficiently solved by a FFT, although the amount of data to be communicated between MPI ranks to compute the Fourier transform is usually not negligible[11, 12].

2.2 Benchmark results

2.2.1 Lennard-Jones

For a typical LJ gas at 50% volume fraction, the efficiency decreases approximately linearly with the logarithm of the number of cores, falling below 50% at 512 cores (Figure 2). The performance increases roughly linearly with the number of cores (data not shown).

We plan on **improving the weak scaling characteristic by removing synchronization barriers in the communication code and optimizing the Verlet list management** to avoid superfluous cache invalidation (Task 2.2, University of Stuttgart). Moreover, we plan to **optimize the memory layout of the particles to improve node-level performance**.

Figure 2: Weak scaling efficiency of a LJ simulation on HPC Vega.

2.2.2 Ionic liquid

For a typical LJ ionic fluid at 25% volume fraction, the efficiency of the CPU implementation decreases rapidly with the number of cores, reaching a 20% plateau at 256 cores (blue curve in Figure 3). The simulation box was constrained to a cube, such that each MPI rank contains a rectangular slice of the box. This was necessary to obtain maximal performance from the FFT library, which can lose up to 20 percentage points of efficiency when the number of mesh points in all three directions is not identical.

The poor scaling profile is due to the inefficient use of the three-dimensional FFT library in ESPResSo, which is currently used in pure MPI mode, and thus doesn't make use of shared memory. Three-dimensional Fourier transforms require several synchronization points, thus making them communication-limited[11].

The GPU weak scaling (orange curve in Figure 3) also decreases rapidly with the number of cores, since the entire particle information must be communicated to MPI rank 0. Currently, ESPResSo can only use one GPU per simulation, and it can only be accessed from MPI rank 0. In terms of performance, the GPU implementation is about three times faster than the CPU implementation (data not shown).

2.2.3 Hydrodynamics

For a typical LB fluid without thermalization, the efficiency of the CPU implementation quickly reaches a 50% plateau at 16 cores (blue curve in Figure 4). The GPU implementation doesn't scale (orange curve in Figure 4) because the LB fluid data structure for the entire simulation has to fit on a single GPU.

In terms of performance, the GPU implementation is about three orders of magnitude faster than the CPU implementation (Figure 5). In other words, 1000 CPU cores are needed to reach the performance of a single-core, single-accelerator simulation. However, this plot can be misleading in two ways. First the CPU implementation allows us to simulate much larger length-scales, since the system is partitioned over a large number of CPU cores. On the contrary, the GPU memory is quickly exhausted as the number of CPU cores increases, which is why the orange curve doesn't extend beyond 8 cores. Second, the GPU implementation relies on single-precision floating point numbers, while the CPU implementation relies on double-precision floating point numbers, thus doubling the bandwidth.

Note: since LB is a bandwidth-limited problem, there is no saturation curve. Choosing the "right" LB fluid domain size per CPU core is simply a question of maxing out the available RAM, at which point the maximal performance is obtained. The LB benchmark was set up with a 128x128x64 unit cell per core to use 500 MB of RAM per core.

Figure 3: Weak scaling efficiency of a ionic liquid simulation on HPC Vega.

Figure 4: Weak scaling efficiency of an unthermalized LB fluid simulation on HPC Vega.

Figure 5: Performance of an unthermalized LB fluid simulation on HPC Vega.

3 Pathway to exascale

3.1 Planned work

3.1.1 Removing synchronization barriers and improving cache re-use

When calculating short-range forces between particles, ESPResSo leverages Newton’s third law to halve the computational cost of pairwise potentials: instead of evaluating the forces and torques on $N(N - 1)$ particles, one can evaluate $N(N - 1)/2$ forces and torques on particle pairs, and use momentum conservation to deduce the counter-forces and counter-torques. In addition, the spatial domain on each CPU core is further divided into subdomains, or “cells”, whose dimensions are larger than the pairwise interaction distance cutoff. The particles in each cell can only interact with particles in the central cell and in the 26 neighboring cells (in 3 dimensions). This technique is known as the “cell list” method. It can be combined with the “Verlet list” method, which assigns to half of the particles a list of all neighboring particles within interaction range (Figure 6). Since the neighborhood calculation is expensive, the Verlet list is recycled for several time steps, and is re-calculated as soon as a neighboring particle steps too far away from the central particle.

The current implementation in ESPResSo has a drawback: particles in the ghost layer must communicate forces and torques to their corresponding particle in the domain they originate from. Since multiple ghost particles may exist for a single particle (e.g. a particle in a box corner), the reduction operation must introduce synchronization barriers to guarantee that particle forces and torques are accumulated sequentially.

We will eliminate this reduction operation by treating local particles and ghost particles differently: local particles will follow the aforementioned integration scheme when interacting with another local particle, however when interacting with a ghost particle, the force and torque will be calculated on the local particle unconditionally, i.e. Newton’s third law won’t be leveraged. While the workload per CPU core will increase slightly due to the extra calculation, the ghost communication will no longer entail a force and torque reduction, since the corresponding local particles will always have up-to-date forces and torques. In this way, we are trading communication for re-calculation.

We also plan on optimizing the Verlet list management. Currently, the cache for the whole system can be invalidated by the motion of a single particle, leading to frequent recalculation of the particle neighborhood. To remediate this issue, **we will partition the Verlet lists** such that they get updated on a per-particle basis, and only when necessary.

Figure 6: Illustration of a two-dimensional slice of a cell system. The local spatial domain (green squares) contains local particles (brown circles) that interact with each other and with ghost particles (white circles) from the ghost layer (white squares) up to a distance r^{cut} . Particles are partitioned in cell lists (black subdivisions) with spacing $r^{\text{cell}} > r^{\text{cut}}$. The Verlet list (pastel circle) stores references to particles in the vicinity of the central particle up to r^{Verlet} . Typically, $r^{\text{Verlet}} = r^{\text{cut}} + r^{\text{skin}}$, with a tunable parameter r^{skin} that controls the trade-off between memory usage and performance: large r^{skin} values lead to better Verlet list re-use at the expense of an increased memory footprint, while small r^{skin} values increase the frequency of Verlet list re-calculation but reduce their memory footprint.

3.1.2 Rolling out a more efficient particle data layout

The particle cells are implemented as an Array of Structures (AoS), i.e. each element in the cell is a particle structure containing the position, velocity, angular velocity, force, torque, electrical charge, dipole moment, and optional data members which are only relevant to specific simulation methods. This strided memory layout is quite inefficient, since only a handful of particle structures can fit inside a memory page, and each cache miss introduces a performance penalty due to the RAM latency.

With a Structure of Arrays (SoA), particle properties are stored contiguously in separate lists. Modern computers can fit 512 to 1024 double-precision values in a memory page, which means that pairwise force kernels can process the forces of about 170 to 340 particles per memory page. This is extremely advantageous, and the computational cost of converting the SoA to an AoS at the beginning of every time step and back at the end of every time step has been shown to be outweighed by the speed-up from pairwise potential kernels[13]. In addition, it has been shown that padding vectors of size three like particle forces, velocities and positions with a fourth unused value was beneficial on architectures that support vectorization[14, 15].

ESPResSo already implements the code necessary to convert data layouts from AoS to SoA and back, and uses it for all GPU force kernels and several CPU force and torque kernels (e.g. the Scalable Fast Coulomb Solver (ScaFaCoS) and Stokesian Dynamics). **We plan on adapting the short-range force kernels to use SoA data layouts.** This will benefit the LJ scenario, and simulations containing charges too, as the P³M electrostatics solver also includes short-range forces for the real-space contribution.

3.1.3 Improving scalability of the electrostatics solver

As part of MultiXscale, high-performance and portable electrostatics solvers are being developed using Kokkos[16] (Task 2.3, Forschungszentrum Jülich). Once this becomes available, we plan to leverage it in ESPResSo to obtain better scalability for systems containing charged particles.

The P³M algorithm consists of two parts: first, short-range interactions are calculated in real-space in a similar fashion to LJ forces. Hence the scalability of this part will benefit from the planned improvements to the LJ scenario, discussed in the previous section. Second, the long-range part of the electrostatic interactions is calculated by solving Poisson's equation in Fourier space. FFT algorithms are inherently limited by memory and network bandwidth[11], making simulations on large number of cores challenging for both CPU and GPU implementations[17]. Likely, most performance benefit for that part can be derived by performing the three-dimensional Fourier transform in a single shared memory locality for the entire simulation. It is expected that the avoidance of MPI-communication for the FFT will strongly overcompensate the communication cost of gathering and scattering the Fourier grid to and from one MPI rank.

3.1.4 Using more efficient lattice-Boltzmann code for hydrodynamics

To improve scalability of fluid simulations, the original LB code in ESPResSo is currently being replaced by the Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAngen (waLBerla) library (Task 3.4, University of Stuttgart), which is designed for HPC environments[18]. We also plan on **making ESPResSo capable of using more than one GPU device, and to make these GPU devices accessible from multiple MPI ranks.** We expect the new GPU implementation in ESPResSo to scale well with the number of GPU devices, as waLBerla is known to scale up to 2048 GPU devices without significant performance drop (Figure 6 in [19]).

The interface code that bridges waLBerla to ESPResSo will be made available as an easily re-usable and extensible stand-alone library, so that other molecular dynamics codes like Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) can couple to waLBerla with minimal effort (Task 3.4, University of Stuttgart). In addition, **a parallel input/output feature will be written to read and write simulation trajectories in a standardized and portable format, with the goal of improving interoperability between ESPResSo and the other simulation codes involved in MultiXscale.**

4 Conclusion and outlook

In this report, we discussed the performance of the current release version of ESPResSo, 4.2.1. The benchmarks show that, while the code can be run in a highly parallel fashion, the scalability of some algorithms is not optimal. Most importantly, the three-dimensional Fourier transform underpinning the electrostatics solver do not scale well, and ESPResSo is currently limited to a single GPU controlled by MPI rank 0. We described the planned work to improve the scalability and performance of the software for the three simulation scenarios (LJ particles, charged particles, LB hydrodynamics). Let us conclude this report by describing a specific simulation scenario as it pertains to the demonstrator planned in MultiXscale WP 4.

Typical simulations in the field of charged soft matter and energy materials combine all three scenarios we chose for the benchmarks. These simulations will contain a large number of charged particles, which additionally interact via the LJ interaction. A lot of the relevant systems contain a solvent, such as water. Hence, when dynamics is of interest, hydrodynamic interactions typically cannot be neglected, so the particles are coupled to a LB hydrodynamics solver. Last but not least, at the typical length scale of nanometers to microns, thermal fluctuation (Brownian motion) play a crucial role. Hence these simulations contain random forces and are stochastic in nature.

A simulation campaign as it is envisioned for the demonstrator would consist of parameter sweeps over properties such as ion concentration and electrode properties, resulting in approximately 100 parameter sets. For each of these parameter sets, an average over 5 to 10 simulations is taken, to account for the stochastic nature of the simulations resulting from Brownian motion. Hence 500 to 1000 simulations would be run.

For ESPResSo 4.2.1, a simulation with one million charged particles on 1024 cores will currently takes 20 ms per time step, which amounts to 55 hours for a typical simulation length of ten million time steps. In total the simulation campaign described above would therefore consume 30 to 60 million core hours.

Using the current ESPResSo version, only the CPU implementation of LB could be used, as the memory of the single supported GPU is insufficient. This would add approximately another 50 ms per time step, and triple the computation time.

Given the performance of ESPResSo 4.2.1, such campaigns are rarely run. What we envision is:

- Once ESPResSo is capable of making use of the multi-GPU support for the LB method, hydrodynamics can be added to a simulation as described above without increasing the time-to-solution. This would be achieved by off-loading LB to the GPU, for which it is very well suited.
- Reduce the overall time-to-solution with the improvements planned for short-range calculation. If, for example, the efficiency of the electrostatics solver could be improved from 20% to 40% at 1024 cores, the time-to-solution would be halved to approximately one day.

Considering the development process on a complex software package implementing a large amount of different algorithms, it will be difficult to achieve both goals at the same time. Therefore, we are going to prioritize the use of many GPUs over the most efficient use of the CPUs, as the GPUs contribute the majority of floating point operations per second (FLOPS) and memory bandwidth in today's supercomputers.

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References

Acronyms used

HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
MPI	Message Passing Interface
LB	lattice-Boltzmann
LJ	Lennard-Jones
P ³ M	particle–particle–particle mesh
FFT	fast Fourier transform
SoA	Structure of Arrays
AoS	Array of Structures
FLOPS	floating point operations per second
CDC	carbide-derived carbon

Software mentioned

waLBerla Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAngen
ESPresSo Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems
LAMMPS Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator
ScaFaCoS Scalable Fast Coulomb Solver

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